

**Petrographic Analysis of Egyptian Predynastic Pottery from AKAP
Excavations in the Aswan Region (TECHNOPREGYPT
2021/43/P/HS3/03262) – Preliminary Report**

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Introduction

This petrographic study has been carried out in the frame of the project TECHNOPREGYPT *Ceramic technology and the socio-political environment of Predynastic Egypt* (2021/43/P/HS3/03262). The analysis aimed to characterize a variety of pottery fabrics from the 5th and 4th millennium BCE from the sites investigated by the Aswan-Kom Ombo Archaeological project (AKAP) directed by M. C. Gatto and A. Curci in the First Nile Cataract Region. Of particular interest was any continuation in raw material selection over time within the various traditions identified. Information on technology and paste recipes was vital for understanding this corpus and relating the data to previous petrographic studies of analogous Predynastic material from seven sites to the north (Naqada, Abydos, Turah, Maadi, Buto, Tell el-Farhkha, and Tell Iswid).

Methodology and material

Thirty-three samples were selected by Maria Carmela Gatto and Jade Bajéot, and the thin sections were prepared and analyzed at the Kom Ombo and Aswan storehouses. The sites included in the analysis were investigated by the AKAP team directed by M. C. Gatto and A. Curci, and are: WAL10, two 5th mill. tumuli tombs at Wadi al-Lawi; SN1 a large 5th mill. tumulus tomb at Shaab Nagema; WK15 and WK14, a predynastic settlement and its cemetery at Nag el-Qarmila; NH16, a predynastic funerary complex at Nag el-Hamdulab; WT27, predynastic settlement remains at Wadi el-Tawil; predynastic cemetery SM6 and Pre-Kerma/B-Group camp SM22 at Sheik-Mohamed (see Table 1).

The analysis of the thin sections with a petrographic microscope at 100x magnification followed standard procedures (see Reedy 2008). For each section its colour in plane (PPL) and cross polarized (XPL) light was noted, an estimate was made for the frequency of inclusions relative to clay matrix, and the sorting of the inclusions was specified. The minerals identified in the thin section were listed by those that represent the main inclusions, and those that are less common. For the inclusions, both their general shape and size range were noted. Information on raw material source comes from the Geologic Map of Egypt (1981) and from extensive previous petrographic work on Egyptian pottery (see Ownby and Brand 2019).

The petrographic groups have been distinguished based on the identified clay type and dominant material in the paste whether plant remains, sand, and/or a calcium carbonate component. However, many samples have a range of these materials present in the fabric. The results present the analyzed sherds by the techno-petrographic groups determined during the technological analysis, elaborated by Jade Bajéot during the project TECHNOPREGYPT (2021/43/P/HS3/03262) and of previous research (Bajéot and Buechez 2021; Bajéot et al. 2024).

Sample #	Period	Description	Petrographic Group	Techno-petrographic group
WAL10.1	5 th mill. BCE	Open form with direct rim	Shale clay	MNR
WAL10.2	5 th mill. BCE	Open form with direct rim, burnished int./ext., rippled ext.	Nile clay	MNR
SN1.1	5 th mill. BCE	Open form with direct rim, rippled ext./int.	Nile clay	MNR
SN1.2	5 th mill. BCE	Open form with direct rim, burnished int./ext., rippled ext.	Nile clay	MNR
WT27.1	Predynastic	Non-diagnostic sherd	Marl clay	NAQ-MARL
WT27.2	Predynastic	Cup with direct rim	Nile clay	MNR
WT27.3	Predynastic	Brown burnished bowl with direct rim	Nile clay	MNR
NH16.4	Predynastic	Red-polished bowl	Mixed (shale)	NAQ-MIXED
NH16.5	Predynastic	Wavy-Handled jar	Mixed (shale)	NAQ-MIXED
NH16.6	Predynastic	Wavy-Handled jar	Nile clay	NAQ-SILT
NH16.7	Predynastic	Red-polished wine jar	Marl clay	NAQ-MARL
NH16.10	Predynastic	Wavy-Handled jar	Mixed (shale)	NAQ-MIXED
NH16.11	Predynastic	Fragment of rounded base, rippled ext.	silty Nile clay	MNR
NH16.12	Predynastic	N-Ware bowl (Petrie 1921), impressed and incised decoration on the outside	silty Nile clay	Undetermined
NH16.13	Predynastic	Black-Mouthed closed form with direct rim, rippled ext.	silty Nile clay	MNR
NH16.14	Predynastic	Open form with direct rim, burnished ext.	Calcareous	MNR
SM6.15	Predynastic	Red painted ware	silty Nile clay	Not analyzed
WK14.1	Predynastic	Black-Mouthed deep open form, burnished int./ext.	Nile clay	MNR
WK14.2	Predynastic	Black-Mouthed open form with direct rim, milled rim, rippled ext. burnished int./ext.	silty Nile clay	MNR
WK14.3	Predynastic	Black-Topped beaker with direct rim	silty Nile clay	NAQ-SILT
WK14.4	Predynastic	Black-Topped beaker slightly everted rim	silty Nile clay	NAQ-SILT
WK14.5	Predynastic	Black-Topped bowl with direct rim	silty Nile clay	NAQ-SILT
WK14.6	Predynastic	Red-Polished bowl	silty Nile clay	NAQ-SILT
WK14.7	Predynastic	Red-Polished bowl	very silty Nile clay	NAQ-SILT
WK14.8	Predynastic	Bowl with direct rim, burnished int./ext.	Shale clay	SHAPE
WK14.9	Predynastic	Wavy-Handled jar	Mixed (shale)	NAQ-MIXED
WK14.10	Predynastic	Basin/very large bowl, smoothed int./ext.	Mixed (shale)	NAQ-MIXED
WK14.11	Predynastic	Open form, smoothed int./ext.	Shale clay	SHAPE
WK14.12	Predynastic	Open form, smoothed int./ext.	Shale clay	SHAPE
WK15.1	Predynastic	Open form, smoothed int./ext.	Shale clay	SHAPE
WK15.2	Predynastic	Black-Mouthed	silty Nile clay	MNR
SM22.16	Pre-Kerma/B-Group (3 rd mill. BCE)	Black-Mouthed bowl with simple impressed decoration	silty Nile clay	Not analyzed
SM22.17	Pre-Kerma/B-Group (3 rd mill. BCE)	Bowl, smoothed int./ext., incised decoration ext.	silty Nile clay	Not analyzed

Table 1: Sample list.

Results

MNR technical tradition

The samples of this group have in common the *chaîne opératoire* that sees the construction of the pots with a spiraled coil for the base and small coils fixed by internal apposition for the walls. The shape was finalized by percussion, laying the vessel on a hole on the ground or on a mold covered by a mat (which often leaves the characteristic rippled texture) and hammering the leather hard pot from the inside (for more details see Bajeot et al. 2024). This technical tradition is very long-lasting as it is found at least from the 5th to the 3rd mill. BCE.

5th mill. BCE samples

Four samples of this tradition and dating to the 5th mill. BCE were analyzed petrographically. Samples SN1.1 and SN1.2 (open forms with direct rim and rippled decoration) both have a typical Nile clay paste with natural inclusions. The firing temperature was probably around 800°C or slightly below. Both have notable epidote (though very rare) and likely siltstone rock fragments. Such features could suggest production in the Aswan area where siltstone/sandstone is common and epidote from granite more prevalent (see Geological Map of Egypt). Sample WL10.1 (open form with direct rim) has a shale clay with common shale fragments, some black and others red. Other inclusions are quartz, feldspars, and rare mica and pyroxene. Some Nile clay may be present in the paste, and could be a natural part of the raw materials. Very rare sandstone and siltstone rock fragments could indicate the wider Aswan area as a source. The firing temperature was probably from 750°C to 800°C. Sample WL10.2 (open form with direct rim and rippled decoration) has a Nile clay paste with some medium-sized grains. A single siltstone fragment could indicate a source in southern Egypt where Nubian sandstone (with siltstone) is present (Geologic Map of Egypt). The firing temperature was probable from 800°C and 850°C.

4th mill. BCE samples

Eight sherds of the MNR technical tradition were examined in thin section and dated to the 4th mill. BCE. Most vessels have a paste of fine Nile clay with common silty quartz and a few medium sized grains. Two are ripple ware vessels. Sample WK15.2, a black-mouthed pot, is also of this very fine Nile clay paste. NH16.11 also had some fine limestone fragments in the paste. The firing temperature was probably between 750°C and 800°C. Sample NH16.13 is the same but with one fine-sized fragment of calcrete (recrystallized calcium carbonate developed on soil deposits) and rare larger grains. Sample WT27.2, a cup, had a paste of Nile clay with natural inclusions up to coarse in size for a few grains. The firing temperature was probably between 800°C and 850°C.

Sample SM6.15, a red-painted ware, has a Nile clay but with more common calcrete ranging from fine to medium in size. Ash or carbonized plant remains (from a reduced firing) are notably present. The firing temperature was probably from 750°C to 800°C. Sample WK14.1, a Black-Mouthed form, has a silty Nile clay but also includes some medium-sized and rare coarse-sized grains. Calcrete fragments are frequent. The firing temperature was likely above 800°C. With a similar temperature at firing is Sample WK14.2, also a Black-Mounted form, but with the more typical silty Nile clay. Calcrete is absent. Sample WT27.3, while having Nile clay, has notable inclusions of calcrete and likely biotite schist. This makes the sample unusual as schist derives from the Eastern Desert. The brown-burnished bowl with direct rim was probably fired close to 800°C.

Sample NH16.14, an open form with direct rim, has a brown calcareous clay with only common microfossils as the inclusions. Many appear to be from coralline algae, and possibly *Amphrioa* sp. This would suggest Pliocene to Quaternary deposits that are not within the Aswan area, but are found along the coast of Egypt. The vessel was undoubtedly low fired, below 800°C.

3rd mill. BCE samples

Two Post-Kerma/B-Group vessels dating to the 3rd mill. BCE were petrographically examined. Sample SM22.16, a Black-Mouthed bowl with impressed decoration, has a Nile clay with only rare calcrete and mostly silty quartz. Sample SM22.17, bowl with incised decoration, has a Nile

clay with some inclusions up to medium size. Both appear to have some plant remains (but unlikely dung). The firing temperature was probably the same for both, up to 850°C.

NAQ technical tradition

4th mill. BCE samples

The *chaîne opératoire* that characterizes this group sees the construction of the pots with a spiraled coil for the base and coils fixed by internal apposition for the walls. The leather hard clay was shaved by cutting away chips of clay to thin the walls and finalize the shape. Within this group we have several fabrics and finishes, differentiated on the basis of the function of the pots. The sub-groups represented by our sample range are NAQ-SILT (levigated Nile clay) and NAQ-MIXED (marl clays, mixed clays with shale) (for more details see Bajeot et al. 2024).

NAQ-SILT included three black-topped vessels of Nile clay with common silty quartz, WK14.3, WK14.4, and WK14.5. The two red polished vessels, WK14.6 and WK14.7, were similar to the black-topped redware. However, Sample WK-14-7 had only very fine to fine, silty quartz with almost no medium-sized inclusions. A Wavy-handled vessel, Sample NH16.6, has a coarser Nile clay with rare plant remains. The firing temperature was probably between 800°C and 850°C for all.

Five Predynastic sherds had a similar paste that has been previously documented and is called the Mixed (shale) clays fabric (see Ownby and Köhler 2021). The paste has fine shale fragments, micritic limestone, and microfossils. Sample NH16.4 is from a red polished bowl, while Sample NH16.5 is from a wavy-handled vessel. The latter has a browner paste that is more calcareous with mostly fine-sized inclusions. Both were probably fired between 750°C and 800°C. Related to these samples is NH-16-10, another wavy-handled vessel. Inclusions are mostly fine in size, while the firing temperature may have been close to 850°C. Sample WK14.9 and WK14.10, a wavy-handled jar and basin respectively, are in this group. The first has mostly fine-sized shale, microfossils, and micritic limestone. The second has less common shale fragments, but the microfossils and limestone are still present. Both were probably fired around 800°C.

Four sherds also appear to derive from shale clays, but not of the previous mixed (shale) fabric. Sample WK14.8, a bowl with direct rim, has tan shale fragments in a shale clay. Some sand and silty quartz are present possibly suggesting a Nile clay component, that could be natural. Rare micritic limestone is present, along with rare fine-grained sandstone rock fragments (possibly suggesting the raw materials are from the Aswan area). The firing temperature was probably up to 800°C. Sample WK14.11 has frequent coarse-sized shale inclusions with some shale fragments also containing silty quartz, which is common in the paste. Very rare are micritic limestone fragments, while siltstone rock fragments are frequent and may suggest the Aswan or Kharga area. The open form vessel was probably fired below 800°C. Sample WK-14-12, also an open form, is quite similar to both but the shale fragments lack silty quartz and micritic limestone is slightly more common. The firing temperature is analogous. Somewhat different is Sample WK15.1, from an open form, with coarse shale fragments and some micritic limestone. Common quartz and feldspars are either sand natural to the secondary shale deposit, or some Nile clay that is also likely inherent to the raw materials. The vessel was probably fired from 750°C to 800°C.

Two marl clay pots were examined. Sample WT-27-1 (unknown form) comprised a grayish marl clay with common fine limestone and fine quartz + feldspars. A few possible shale rock fragments were noted. It was likely fired close to 850°C. Similar is NH-16-7, a red polished wine jar, with more fine inclusions also of quartz and feldspar. The firing temperature is analogous.

Undetermined

As the small size of the few N-Ware sherds analyzed in the course of the TECHOPREGYPT project did not allow for a complete technological analysis, for the moment they have been included in the "undetermined" group. Only one sherd was examined in thin section. A fragment of N-Ware bowl, Sample NH16.12, has a silty, fine Nile clay but with rare medium to coarse sized calcrite. The firing temperature was probably between 750°C and 800°C.

Discussion

This study included a wide range of vessel types from a broad time period. The goal was to assess paste recipe and raw material choice as relates to ceramic tradition and location of production. The fabrics of the samples included in the MNR group, up to Early Dynastic in date, are quite variable although mostly of Nile clay. None of the vessels appear to have the fine paste noted for Nubian pottery from around the 2nd Cataract (but of C-Group and Pan-Grave type) (de Souza and Ownby 2022). Along with inclusions of calcrite, also identified in later Nubian pottery in the current study, this could suggest local production within the Kom Ombo region. However, the 5th millennium vessels are notable distinct and may have been made closer to Aswan. One vessel of this period had a unique shale paste with sandstone that could also indicate the greater Aswan area where shale outcrops or possibly the Kharga Oasis. Production at Hierakonpolis is less likely as that fabric is described as containing limestone and sandstone is less prevalent there (Baba and Freestone 2008). Likewise, two 4th mill. brown burnished bowls were made with distinct raw materials. One is certainly not local but from the coast, while another indicates production in the Eastern Desert. The red-painted vessel may not be local either given the common carbonized plant material, but additional A-Group sherds need to be analyzed.

A number of Predynastic samples of NAQ tradition and Nile clay were analyzed to compare to the MNR Predynastic material. Surprisingly, the pastes are actually finer than those samples and fired in a more oxidizing atmosphere at higher temperatures. Further, calcrite was not identified suggesting a different raw material source. It is unknown if this would be from within the Kom Ombo/Aswan area or from elsewhere. More certainly of non-local origin are the samples of the mixed (shale) fabric. The source of this paste has been suggested to be the Qena Bend area, where shale and limestone with microfossils are known (Ownby and Köhler 2021). On the contrary, the samples included in the SHALE group do not have these same features, but have sandstone and siltstone and could be from the Aswan area or perhaps the Kharga Oasis, and are similar to the 5th millennium samples described above.

Conclusions

This important study has revealed several significant findings.

- 1) Predynastic Nubian vessels (MNR) were likely made in Egypt
- 2) The MNR tradition is distinct from the NAQ including different raw material choices and/or processing

- 3) This is the furthest south the mixed (shale) fabric used for wavy-handled Predynastic vessels has now been documented indicating an even wider transport network for pots made in the Qena area (now identified at eight sites from the Delta to Aswan)

Such results can be further contextualized based on the vessel types and archaeological contexts. However, this small study has greatly contributed to a better understanding of pottery production, movement, and use for this southern area of Egypt from the earliest periods. Hopefully, additional studies will further clarify these initial findings.

Photos of the samples

The images provided are working photos with the sole purpose of illustrating the samples analyzed.

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Appendix I

Sample #: WT27.1

Colour PPL: dark brown

Colour XPL: dark brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: good

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, micritic limestone

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, amphibole, pyroxene, microcline, chert, shale rock fragments, volcanic rock fragments?

Comments: calcareous (marl) and silty clay, probably fired close to 850°C

Sample #: WT27.2

Colour PPL: reddish brown

Colour XPL: dark reddish brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: fair

Size Range: very fine to coarse

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, amphibole, pyroxene

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, volcanic rock fragments, grog?

Comments: Nile clay with natural inclusions, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: WT27.3

Colour PPL: reddish brown

Colour XPL: dark reddish brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: poor

Size Range: very fine to very coarse

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, amphibole, pyroxene

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, nari/chalk, metamorphic rock fragments (schist?), chert?

Comments: Nile clay with natural inclusions and notable nari/chalk, likely schist, probably fired around 800°C

Sample #: NH16.4

Colour PPL: reddish brown

Colour XPL: reddish brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: fair

Size Range: very fine to coarse

Shape Range: angular to rounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments, micritic limestone, microfossils

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, calcite, chert, pyroxene, amphibole, biotite, muscovite

Comments: mixed (shale) fabric, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C

Sample #: NH16.5

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 30%

Sorting: good

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments, micritic limestone, microfossils

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, calcite, chert, pyroxene

Comments: mixed (shale) fabric, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C

Sample #: NH16.6

Colour PPL: reddish brown

Colour XPL: dark reddish brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 30%

Sorting: fair
Size Range: very fine to coarse
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, amphibole, pyroxene, OPL, volcanic rock fragments
Comments: Nile clay with natural inclusions and rare plant remains, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: NH16.7

Colour PPL: dark brown
Colour XPL: very dark brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: good
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, micritic limestone (mostly decomposed)
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, pyroxene, amphibole, volcanic rock fragments, shale rock fragments?
Comments: Marl clay with natural inclusions, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: NH16.10

Colour PPL: brown
Colour XPL: dark brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: good
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, micritic limestone, microfossils
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, pyroxene, shale rock fragments,
Comments: mixed (shale) fabric, probably fired just above 800°C

Sample #: NH16.11

Colour PPL: brown
Colour XPL: brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: fair
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, plagioclase, potassium feldspar, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz (some likely quartzite), muscovite, biotite, amphibole, micritic limestone, ash?
Comments: silty Nile clay with rare fine micritic limestone, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C

Sample #: NH16.12

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: fair

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, plagioclase, potassium feldspar, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz (some likely quartzite), muscovite, biotite, amphibole, micritic limestone (nari/chalk), OPL

Comments: silty Nile clay with rare calcareous material, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C

Sample #: NH16.13

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: good

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, plagioclase, potassium feldspar, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz (some likely quartzite), muscovite, biotite, amphibole, micritic limestone (nari/chalk)

Comments: silty Nile clay with rare calcareous material, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C

Sample #: NH16.14

Colour PPL: tan

Colour XPL: tan

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: poor

Size Range: very fine to coarse

Shape Range: subangular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: macrofossils (common *Amphiroa* coralline algae)

Additional Inclusions Present: quartz

Comments: calcareous clay with very common macrofossils, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C

Sample #: SM6.15

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: fair

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, plagioclase, potassium feldspar, iron oxides, opaques, micritic limestone (nari/crust, few with quartz grains), pyroxene, OPL (or ash)

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz (some likely quartzite), muscovite, biotite, amphibole, chert?

Comments: silty Nile clay with some calcareous material and probably carbonized plant remains from the firing or ash, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C

Sample #: SM22.16

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: good

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, amphibole, micritic limestone (nari/chalk), volcanic rock fragments, OPL

Comments: silty Nile clay with rare calcareous material, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: SM22.17

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: fair

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, amphibole, micritic limestone (nari/chalk), OPL

Comments: silty Nile clay with rare calcareous material, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: SN1.1

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: fair

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, amphibole, volcanic rock fragments, chert, epidote, sedimentary rock fragment (siltstone?)

Comments: Nile clay with natural inclusions, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C (could be Aswan with epidote and siltstone)

Sample #: SN1.2

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: fair
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, amphibole, volcanic rock fragments, chert, epidote, zoisite, sedimentary rock fragment (siltstone?), sphene?
Comments: Nile clay with natural inclusions, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C (could be Aswan with epidote and siltstone)

Sample #: WK14.1

Colour PPL: dark brown
Colour XPL: dark brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: fair
Size Range: very fine to coarse
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, amphibole, calcrete, chert
Comments: Nile clay with some calcareous material, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: WK14.2

Colour PPL: dark brown
Colour XPL: dark brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: good
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, amphibole, epidote
Comments: silty Nile clay, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: WK14.3

Colour PPL: dark brown
Colour XPL: dark brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: good
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, amphibole, volcanic rock fragments
Comments: silty Nile clay, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: WK14.4

Colour PPL: dark brown

Colour XPL: dark brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: good
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, microcline, amphibole, volcanic rock fragments, chert
Comments: silty Nile clay, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: WK14.5

Colour PPL: dark brown
Colour XPL: dark brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: good
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, amphibole, volcanic rock fragments
Comments: silty Nile clay, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: WK14.6

Colour PPL: brown
Colour XPL: brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: good
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, amphibole
Comments: silty Nile clay, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C, dark likely hematite slip on one surface

Sample #: WK14.7

Colour PPL: brown
Colour XPL: brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: well
Size Range: very fine to fine
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, amphibole
Comments: very silty Nile clay, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: WK14.8

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 30%

Sorting: poor

Size Range: very fine to very coarse

Shape Range: subangular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, pyroxene, amphibole, micritic limestone, siltstone,

Comments: shale clay with shale fragments and possibly some Nile clay (silty quartz), probably fired between 750°C and 800°C (siltstone could suggest near Aswan area)

Sample #: WK14.9

Colour PPL: reddish brown

Colour XPL: reddish brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: fair

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments, micritic limestone, microfossils

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, biotite, muscovite, pyroxene, amphibole

Comments: mixed (shale) fabric, probably fired just above 800°C

Sample #: WK14.10

Colour PPL: reddish brown

Colour XPL: reddish brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%

Sorting: good

Size Range: very fine to medium

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments, micritic limestone, microfossils

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, biotite, muscovite, pyroxene, amphibole, calcite, nummulite fragment

Comments: mixed (shale) fabric, probably fired just above 800°C

Sample #: WK14.11

Colour PPL: tan

Colour XPL: tan

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 30%

Sorting: poor

Size Range: very fine to very coarse

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments (some have silty quartz)

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, pyroxene, micritic limestone, siltstone, zircon?

Comments: shale clay with natural inclusions, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C (siltstone could suggest near Aswan area or Kharga)

Sample #: WK14.12

Colour PPL: tan

Colour XPL: tan

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 30%

Sorting: poor

Size Range: very fine to very coarse

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, pyroxene, micritic limestone, siltstone

Comments: shale clay with natural inclusions, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C (siltstone could suggest near Aswan area or Kharga)

Sample #: WK15.1

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brownish tan

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 30%

Sorting: poor

Size Range: very fine to very coarse

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, pyroxene, amphibole, micritic limestone

Comments: shale clay with possibly Nile clay or natural sand, probably fired between 750°C and 800°C

Sample #: WK15.2

Colour PPL: brown

Colour XPL: brown

Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 50%

Sorting: well

Size Range: fine to very fine

Shape Range: angular to subrounded

Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene, amphibole

Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, volcanic rock fragments

Comments: very fine, silty Nile clay with natural inclusions, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C

Sample #: WL10.1

Colour PPL: reddish brown
Colour XPL: reddish brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: fair
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, iron oxides, opaques, shale rock fragments
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, muscovite, biotite, amphibole, pyroxene, chert, siltstone, sandstone, metamorphic rock fragment?
Comments: shale and likely Nile clay mix (could be natural), probably fired between 750°C and 800°C (likely in the Aswan area due to siltstone)

Sample #: WAL10.2

Colour PPL: brown
Colour XPL: brown
Frequency of Inclusions (estimated): 40%
Sorting: fair
Size Range: very fine to medium
Shape Range: angular to subrounded
Main Inclusions: quartz, potassium feldspar, plagioclase, muscovite, biotite, iron oxides, opaques, pyroxene
Additional Inclusions Present: polycrystalline quartz, amphibole, siltstone rock fragment, volcanic rock fragments?, OPL?
Comments: Nile clay with natural inclusions, probably fired between 800°C and 850°C (possibly the Aswan area due to siltstone)